

The 5S Methodology in Research Data Management

Structuring and maintaining
file organization

Developed by the Thuringian Competence Network for Research Data Management

Contributors: Kevin Lang (Bauhaus-Universität Weimar)
Annett Schrötter (Friedrich-Schiller Universität Jena)
Roman Gerlach (Friedrich-Schiller Universität Jena)
Jessica Rex (Technische Universität Ilmenau)
Nadine Neute (Universität Erfurt)
Anne Lehmann (Universität Erfurt)

Version: 1.0, 08.02.2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4494258

All texts are licensed as:
[CC0 1.0 Universell Public Domain Dedication](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/)

All comics are licensed as:
[CC BY-NC 4.0 Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/)

5S – Meaning and origin

The 5S methodology is a model for handling research data (comparable to the FAIR principles), which contains 5 steps with the catch phrases beginning with "S" for easy recognition. The steps are intended to help researchers establish an ordered structure for research data and to maintain the system.

The origin of the 5S methods comes from the Japanese philosophy and concept of "Kaizen", which roughly translates to: "The act of making bad things better". This method has been effectively implemented in the Toyota production system since the 1950s, which is why it is referred to as "a Japanese business philosophy of continuous improvement of work practices, personal efficiency, etc." in the New Oxford American Dictionary. Based on this philosophy, Toyota designed five steps that are intended to improve the production process using various methods.

	Japanese (5S)	English (5S)	German (5A)
1	Seiri (整理)	Sort	Aussortieren
2	Seiton (整頓)	Set in Order	Aufräumen
3	Seisō (清掃)	Shine	Arbeitsplatzsauberkeit
4	Seiketsu (清潔)	Standardize	Anordnung zur Regel machen
5	Shitsuke (躰)	Sustain	Alle Punkte einhalten und verbessern

Since the Japanese terms are difficult to read and understand outside of Asia, an equivalent model was developed in the English language. This also consists of five phrases that start with the letter "S". A German translation according to the same scheme turned out to be difficult, which is why the methods were rewritten starting with the letter "A". Therefore, in addition to the international 5S, one also sometimes speaks of the 5A methodology in Germany.

Other well-known manufacturing companies such as Boeing or Hewlett-Packard have also established the methodology in their companies. However, the methods are not only used for production, but also for administrative organization or security guidelines. It quickly became apparent that the use of the 5S methodology is not only suitable for optimizing production processes, but can also improve the process of knowledge acquisition and project workflows. In 2019, the University of Helsinki created a link to research data and presented the methods on its website and as part of the RDA 15th Plenary in 2020 in the form of a poster.

1st step:

Sort

In the first step "Sort" unnecessary data in the project should be deleted. This not only recovers storage space but also keeps track of the most important data and helps you find your way around a smaller number of files.

Implementation of "Sort"

First of all, unnecessary files, duplicates and old versions should be deleted. Even if these are often kept as a backup, the actual backup should be done by a separate system. It is practically impossible to manually back up all of your files. In addition to the time required for this, one would quickly lose track of all versions and copies. It is therefore recommended to use a backup system that creates automatic copies (e.g. according to the 3-2-1 backup rules) and to use a versioning system that documents the work steps on the files and thus makes them easier to restore.

Delete via context menu in Ubuntu 20.04

```
10 # Java class files
11 *.class
12
13 # Generated files
14 bin/
15 gen/
16 out/
```

GitHub: [Android.gitignore](https://github.com/Android/gitignore)

Various temporary files can arise during project work. Many programs generate these, for example, to log their processes, to temporarily store files for certain sections or to restore project data in the event of a crash. At the end of the project at the latest, you don't want to store these files anymore. It is therefore recommended not to use your versioning system (such as git) to log unwanted files (using ".gitignore", see an excerpt on the left). A command can be used, instead, to instruct the system to delete all unwanted files in a project (like all files ending with ".temp"). Of course, it should be carefully analyzed which files are still important for the programs and which can be deleted without problems.

One final point is the fact that certain files simply cannot be deleted or should not be deleted at this point. This is often the case when, for example, a permanent application (such as a server) accesses a file over a long period of time so it is blocked for other operations (such as deletion processes). So that this file is not forgotten, you should either move it (if that is possible) to a folder whose contents are marked for later deletion or mark the file itself. Some systems allow attaching so-called tags or similar markings to files, which makes it easier to find the files to be deleted later.

Screenshot von Software [TagSpaces](https://tagspaces.com/)

2nd step:

Set in order

In the second step "Set in order" folders and files are to be organized in such a way that work areas in a project can be better mapped and certain files can be found more easily. This saves time when working with the data and people involved can find their way around the project more easily at first glance.

Implementation of "Set in order"

- ▼ project_folder
 - ▼ 0_project_management
 - 0_proposals
 - 1_finance
 - 2_reports
 - 3_approvals
 - ▼ 1_empirical
 - 0_input
 - 1_code
 - 2_data_analysis
 - 3_output
 - ▼ 2_paper
 - 0_literature
 - 1_graphics
 - 2_main_text
 - ▼ 3_dissemination
 - 0_presentations
 - 1_publications
 - 2_publicity

First, a folder structure should be created that corresponds to the work areas within a project. In the sciences, these are mostly areas such as project finances, presentations, publications, studies, source code or literature. Since sorting the folders by the first letter is often not useful, because certain areas can be more important than others, the names of the folders can begin with a number so that the operating system can sort them automatically. This can be, for example, "01_studies" or "03_publications". As a rule of thumb, with approx. 7 elements in width, all folders should be manageable and no more than 3 folder levels should be created to avoid unnecessary navigation steps within the folder structure.

As indicated in the last paragraph, the naming convention of the folders and files plays an important role. Using those, the system can automatically carry out certain sortings procedures and as a person, you can already see at first glance which contents a folder or file contains. To be able to access the content of a file quickly, the name should contain meta-information, e.g. date of publication, author, organization or title. By specifying a date in the order year-month-day at the beginning of the file name, the system automatically sorts files correctly on a timeline. Another issue is using the correct characters. Depending on the system or software, using different characters for naming conventions can

lead to problems when processing files. It is therefore recommended to only use lowercase letters, underscores or hyphens in file names instead of spaces and no special characters such as periods or question marks. An exemplary name for a publication file might look like this:

"20201104_tkfdm_fact_sheet_open_source_software.pdf"

Since titles or other meta-information can be quite long, it should be noted here that the file name, including the path of the folder structure, on all common systems must not be longer than 255 characters. Care should therefore be taken to use descriptions that are as short as possible.

Of course, it is not always possible to see at first glance which files can be found in which folders. It is therefore advisable to create a readme file, a wiki page or something similar at an early stage of the project that describes why this folder structure was chosen and where you can roughly find which files.

3rd step:

Shine

In the third step "Shine" the order that has been created should be maintained. Typical deviations from the target state can be identified over time through regular checks. Non-functional structures, on the other hand, catch the eye more quickly and can be adapted.

Implementation of "Shine"

It should be checked at regular intervals whether the established order and organizational structure arising from the first two 5S steps are being adhered to. At the end of a working day or after reaching a previously defined milestone, the newly added files can be checked for completeness, correct naming and correct classification in the structure. Redundant and/or obsolete items are deleted after it has been verified that a more recent file exists and that the current file should

not be retained as an intermediate result. At the same time, this check ensures that the current files contain the current work results and that new copies of older files are not accidentally considered as current versions by the system.

Project documentation has to be updated whenever new work steps or programs are introduced or variables or measurement settings have been changed within experiments. If work steps within the project are not digital, but are documented on paper (e.g. field observations, incoming invoices, etc.), it makes sense to digitize the documents for storage in the existing folder structure to keep the workplace paper-free and the documentation completely digital. If this procedure is impractical, at least the storage location and a brief summary of the documents should be kept in the appropriate place as a reference to simplify the search for the physical materials.

In order for the daily polishing of your work environment to truly fulfill its purpose, it is helpful to briefly document the deviations of the actual from the target state. If, for example, certain errors occur frequently in folder naming and assignment, or if structures become too large and thus confusing, you should think about adapting the structure or changing your work environment to make it easier to maintain the structure.

4th step:

Standardize

In the fourth step "Standardize" best practices are summarized into rules and guidelines and shared with the employees to ensure their acceptance in the facility. If available, established research community standards should be used.

Implementation of "Standardize"

To document the standard procedure, especially for work groups or consortia that work in common directories and/or often share files, the creation of an SOP (Standard Operation Procedure) document is recommended. It contains the standardized procedure as a binding textual description and is mostly divided into objectives, scope, description of the workflow and responsibilities. The SOP may define the organizational structure and designation of folders and files as well as describing the handling of the files:

- How are folders structured?
- What are the naming conventions for the folders and files?
- In which formats are the files being stored?
- What are procurement measures and storage locations?
- What rights and obligations do you have to use the files?
- Which international and/or discipline-specific standards are being adopted and applied?

SOPs should be stored centrally and be easily available to all team members. If working in large teams, it can make sense to limit the access rights to certain folders and files and, for example, to give people read-only rights. If people from different workgroups work on shared laboratory equipment PCs, for example, a notice at the workplace, which summarizes the standards in a short and visualized form, can serve as a reminder to the user of the procedure and thus, facilitate collaborative work.

When publishing data and working with external colleagues, international and discipline-specific standards should be used. Associations such as the International Organization for Standardization, or ISO for short, set standards for the use of timestamps, location information etc. Which format is to be used in the respective specialist area is not always clearly defined. The German Research Foundation (DFG) funds the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in order to align the handling of research data in its consortia, depending on the subject area.

5th step:

Sustain

In the fifth step "Sustain" some discipline is required. This is the most difficult step, because following the rules and standards should become a daily routine. The standardized procedure should be internalized by the employees in such a way that it can be applied without thinking about it.

Implementation of "Sustain"

Self-discipline is primarily a requirement for each individual team member. Developing a good work ethic is crucial. Improvements can only occur if everyone internalizes the standardized procedure and disciplines themselves to adhere to the rules. Superiors have a special role model function.

The standard working method presented in the fourth step of 5S should be stored centrally and used as an essential part of the introductory information for new employees. It is recommended that the information is presented or recalled at regular intervals (e.g. every six months or annually) in internal group workshops. The following topics can be addressed:

- Organization of folders and files
- Server structure and internal databases
- Backup strategy and versioning tools
- Application software (e.g. for source code or electronic laboratory books)
- Handling of personal data
- Literature management
- Communication tools

Workshops do not only offer an opportunity to present the organizational structure, but also to encourage feedback. Existing structures are regularly checked for their functionality and can be adapted as required.

All of this should be well-documented so that employees do not only receive information in the workshops, but always have access to information about the organization, too. There are various options to choose from. Simple descriptions with text can be done with readme files. The Wikimedia open-source tools are available for displaying larger structures and media, such as images, videos or maps. Alternatively, PDF files with instructions and screenshots can be created, which can easily be exchanged by email, for example. However, these are not recommended because they cannot be managed as centrally as the first two solutions mentioned here.

Readme file on GitHub

Wikimedia Tools for different media

Instructions in PDF file

Sources and further information

The Thuringian Competence Network for Research Data Management

- [Website of TKFDM](#)
- [TKFDM Community on Zenodo](#)
- [5S Data Week](#)
- [Coffee Lecture on 5S Data](#)

5S DATA

- [Helsinki University on 5S Data](#)
- [Poster about 5S Data at RDA](#)
- [Origin of 5S \(report on kanbanize.com\)](#)

Tools and other resources

- Tagging of data (Open-Source, multi-platform):
 - [TagSpaces](#)
 - [TAGSTOO](#)
- Versioning (Open-Source, multi-platform):
 - [Git](#)
 - [SVN](#)
 - [CVS](#)
- [Towards a Standardized Research Folder Structure \(GIN-Tonic Team\)](#)
- [Generator/Konverter für Dateinamenskonventionen](#)
- [Wikimedia](#)
- [Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur \(NFDI\) e. V.](#)
- [Overview about NFDI-Konsortien](#)

Stockimages

- [pixabay.com](#)
- [unsplash.com](#)
- [publicdomainvectors.org](#)